

The Role of Movie In Reflection of Mirror of Politics

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ABSTRACT

Movie, since its very beginning, has been a great medium of reflection of the political changes of the society. Politics being a central object in popular and largely politicize country like India has its impact, influence and converse on every walk of life of this country. Movie as vital life line of this country shapes our shared inner knowledge and has tremendous influence on our society. Movies give an perception into the real picture of public and transnational relations. Movies serve as an important tool in manufacturing the concurrence of the target audience. By remaining pious to the narrowest lines of policy of a government, Movie makers urge to define and review buddies and foes on silver screen. Movie may be taken as an important handwriting of socio- political history of a nation. Now a day's utmost of the Movies continue to be political as its base lies in some testament. Politics and Movie make strange backers. While some of our biggest movies have managed to hold a mirror to the political under belly in the country, some still themselves got victims of the wrath of a many far- reaching politics. Numerous a times, political parties even go to the extent of trying to cash in on a film's fashionability. A Movie isn't only an instrument of communication but it also serves as an organ of propaganda to make or rebuild one's image. Movie besides being a great source of entertainment for the people have always been a mirror to apprise people about what kind of politics and lifestyle is prevalent in different classes of society. Indian film industry has also been reflecting the change in the politics with the passage of time.

Key words: Movies, mirror of politics

I INTRODUCTION

Movie, since its very beginning, has been a great medium of reflection of the political changes of the society. Politics being a central object in popular and largely politicize country like India has its impact, influence and converse on every walk of life of this country. Movie as vital life line of this country shapes our shared inner knowledge and has tremendous influence on our society. Movies give an perception into the real picture of public and transnational relations. Movies serve as an important tool in manufacturing the concurrence of the target audience. By remaining pious to the narrowest lines of policy of a government, Movie makers urge to define and review buddies and foes on silver screen. Movie may be taken as an important handwriting of socio- political history of a nation. Now a day's utmost of the Movies continue to be political as its base lies in some testament. Politics and Movie make strange backers. While some of our biggest movies have managed to hold a mirror to the political under belly in the country, some still themselves got victims of the wrath of a many far- reaching politics. Numerous a times, political parties even go to the extent of trying to cash in on a film's fashionability. A Movie isn't only an instrument of communication but it also serves as an organ of propaganda to make or rebuild one's image.

II RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method used to prepare this research paper is content analysis and review of the Movies made during different era of the Indian politics since its beginning in India in the early 21st century. The data source will consists of a set of national films of 21 century based on elements of political discourse.

III RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design chosen to complete this paper is descriptive as it has been prepared after the study of different books, websites, and magazines and more importantly after watching Movies. In this research paper we have tried to find out the how the films of different genres produced in the country in last several decades reflected the contemporary condition. For this, we have referred to some books, websites giving information about the older movies which we do not easily find in the market.

IV OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To explore dynamics of political discourse as reflected in National films.
2. To study how films use entertaining plots mixed with political content in order to convey messages to the public.
3. To find how politics and entertainment are merged together to influence public opinion.
4. To find how films can be a tool to not only reflect reality but also construct the political ideology
5. To grasp the utility of film as a medium in portrayal of international relations.
6. To interpret the importance of films in understanding foreign policy of a country

V HYPOTHESIS

- National movies have always been a reflection of the political issues of their era.
- National Movies of all the genres whether – comedy, thriller, action, romance or art reflect a particular class or section of political parties and the activities they engage themselves in.
- Movies are one of the most powerful mediums of communication to portray any kind of issue or situation prevalent in secular parties.
- Movies based on political parties benefits also conveys a message to the society and the policymakers and have the power to bring about a change in the society.
- Almost every Movie is based on a plot decided by the filmmaker which ultimately comes from the real-life character, incidents or issues.

VI Role of National Movies in Reflection of the Political Ideologies

There are numerous films based on the lives of Indian politicians. Here are some of the most talked-about films among them.

The Tashkent Files: The 2019's thriller is a cinematic take on the death of the Indian former Prime Minister Lal Bahadur Shastri. Starring Shweta Basu Prasad, Naseeruddin Shah, and Mithun Chakraborty in lead roles, the movie saw a great portrayal of the early days of free India.

Sarkar: ‘Sarkar’, ‘Sarkar Raj’, and ‘Sarkar 3’ are claimed to be influenced by ‘The Godfather’ and partly based on the life of politician Balasaheb Thackeray. ‘Sarkar’, played by actor Amitabh Bachchan, is thought to resemble Thackeray in various ways. In the film, actor Abhishek Bachchan plays Amitabh Bachchan's son. In addition to them, there is actress Katrina Kaif, actor Kay Kay Menon, actress Tanisha Mukherjee, and actress Supriya Pathak in this film directed by filmmaker Ram Gopal Varma. The second part saw the addition of actress Aishwarya Rai. The third part saw the addition of actor Manoj Bajpayee, actor Amit Sadh, actress Yami Gautam, and many others.

Thackeray: ‘Thackeray’, a 2019 film directed by filmmaker Abhijit Panse, is based on the life of political leader Balasaheb Thackeray. He formed the Shiv Sena party in 1966 as a cartoonist. The protagonist was portrayed by actor Nawazuddin Siddiqui, while his wife was played by actress Amrita Rao. In Maharashtra, the right-wing pro-Marathi and Hindu nationalist party is still active and now in power. ‘Thackeray’ wielded considerable power among Maharashtrians, particularly in Mumbai, where he pushed for their rights. He began his career as a cartoonist for the Free Press Journal before launching his own cartoon weekly, Marmik, with his brother. Following the success of Marmik, he founded his own political organisation, Shiv Sena.

An Insignificant Man: The 2016 sociopolitical documentary is centered on Delhi Chief Minister Arvind Kejriwal, who is also the leader of the Aam Aadmi Party. It is about the growth of anti-corruption rallies in India, which resulted in the foundation of the AAP. At the Toronto International Picture Festival, the film earned a standing ovation. Kejriwal, a former bureaucrat, received the Ramon Magsaysay Award for Emergent Leadership for his anti-corruption crusade. Kejriwal served as a joint commissioner of income tax in the Indian Revenue Service before becoming a politician.

Thalaivii: Actress Kangana Ranaut plays late actor-politician Jayalalithaa in the 2021 Indian biographical drama. Actor Arvind Swami plays actor-politician MG Ramachandran in the film. Filmmaker AL Vijay directed the film, which was released in Tamil, Hindi, and Telugu. Jayalalithaa's path as an actor, politician, and female role model in Indian politics is

chronicled in the film. She served as Tamil Nadu's chief minister six times, for a total of 14 years, which is an achievement par excellence.

The Accidental Prime Minister: The 2019 film is based on political analyst Sanjaya Baru's book 'The Accidental Prime Minister'. It starred actor Anupam Kher as then-Prime Minister Manmohan Singh. The film depicts Singh's fall as a victim to the Congress' dynastic attempt to boost politician Rahul Gandhi. Sanjaya Baru was played by actor Akshaye Khanna, politician Priyanka Gandhi was played by actress Aahana Kumra, and politician Sonia Gandhi was played by actress Suzanne Bernert.

PM Narendra Modi: Narendra Modi, who starts off as a poor tea-seller, rises up to several challenges in life and finally gets elected as the 14th Prime Minister of India. The film starring actor Vivek Anand Oberoi in the titular role takes a favourable look at the political career of Narendra Modi, the current Prime Minister of India. It focuses on his life in regional politics before the 2014 election in which he swept to power. How he started from humble beginnings and went on to become the leader of the country is a remarkable journey in itself.

Nayak: The story of a one-day chief minister rose hope in the eyes of many Indians who were sick of dark politics. Starring Anil Kapoor in lead talks about how a news anchor turns into chief minister for one day and changes the whole political scenario of his state.

Peepli Live: Peepli Live Directed by Anusha Rizvi was a satire reflecting the plight of the farmers in the country and the media and political response to the issue, it basically showcases the change, as well as the existing gap between the developed and marginal India. The increasing consumerism among media and also the insensitivity, rather the difference between communication and understanding between rural and urban India is also beautifully reflected in the movie. These were just the snap shots of some of the movies, but if a holistic view of the entire film industry is analyzed, the medium has become popular because of the depiction of the populist sentiments of the Indian society. It is the very fact that people relate to the films and turnout to the theatres. Films, since very beginning, were a mirror reflecting the issues of society. Every kind of issue gets representations in cinema through one film or the other. While films like Peepli Live shows the plight of the farmers and its politicization by the political leaders and media hype films like Shanghai shows how the big real estate players are working in our society and exploiting the middle-class society to make money.

VIII CONCLUSION

The research study will be significant in researching the area of National (Bolly wood) films with a view to uncovering its key attributes that construct political discourse. The aim is to investigate movie representation of political discourse in National film. The reasons for undertaking such a research lie mainly within the salience of political discourse within National films, the inevitable presence of politics in National films, as well as the vast unexplored field of political discourse as approached from movie perspective. Reading film and popular culture diagnostically presents insights into the current political situation, into the strengths and vulnerabilities of the contending political forces, into the hopes and fears of the population. Film thus provides important insights into the psychological, socio-political, and ideological make-up of a specific society at a given point in history. Reading film diagnostically also allows one to detect what ideological solutions to various problems are being offered, and thus to anticipate certain trends, to gain insights into social problems and conflicts, and to appraise the dominant ideologies and emergent oppositional forces. Consequently, diagnostic political critique enables one to perceive the limitations of mainstream conservative and liberal political ideologies, as well as helping to decipher their continuing appeal. It enables one to grasp the utopian yearnings in a given society and challenges progressives to develop cultural representations, political alternatives, and practices and movements which address these predispositions. Such diagnostic reading thus helps with the formulation of progressive political practices which address salient hopes, fears, and desires, and the construction of social alternatives that are grounded in existing psychological, social, and cultural matrixes. Consequently, diagnostic film critique does not merely offer another clever method of reading films but provides weapons of critique for those interested in producing a better society. It can be concluded that films use thrilling & entertaining plots mixed with political content in order to convey their messages to the public. The research work consolidates the idea that films indeed are a great medium of communication that has the immense potential to reflect the socio-economic condition of a society. Indian Movies since its very beginning has been mostly focusing on the social and political issues as a backdrop for their stories. Movie besides being a great source of entertainment for the people have always been a mirror to apprise people about what kind of politics and lifestyle is prevalent in different classes of society. Indian film industry has also been reflecting the change in the political with the passage of time.

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Movies List

- Peepli Live
- Nayak
- PM Narendra Modi
- The Accidental Prime Minister
- Thalaivii
- An Insignificant Man
- Thackeray
- Sarkar
- The Tashkent Files